

Quantitative Analysis of DNA Profiling Attained from Various Conditions of Sternum

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Abstract— The sternum is a partially T-shaped vertical bone that centrally forms the anterior portion of the chest wall. It is divided anatomically into the manubrium, body and xiphoid process. The sternum connects the ribs via the costal cartilage, forming the anterior rib cage. The manubrium is the broad superior segment, the body is the middle portion, and the xiphoid process is a narrower distal segment forming the partial T-shape. Generally, two types of sternum bones are received in the forensic lab in missing identity cases: one wet bone with tissues attached to bone and preserved in a nanoporous container; in contrast, another type is wrapped in gauze/cloth and kept in an envelope to let it dry in normal environmental conditions. Typically, females have a shorter and thinner body of the sternum when compared to males. For forensic examination, forensic pathologists utilized certain chemicals to preserve unknown human body parts taken for identification via DNA analysis. Quantitation of DNA plays a vital role in the analysis of forensic samples like bone, tissues or any other biological material so that forensic pathologists can take the optimum quantity of extracted DNA for amplification and profiling. Analysis of skeletal remains for forensic purposes may include the assessment of the sternum. Often, the forensic pathologist or osteologist aims to establish the forensic identity, which primarily consists of the ethnicity, sex, age and stature of an individual from the skeletal remains subjected to examination. Stature estimation from the sternum is done for the determination of sex, in addition to estimating age and height.

Keywords— Sternum, Sex determination, Stature examination, DNA analysis, DNA profiling

I. INTRODUCTION

In forensic medical investigation, apperception of unrevealed human remnants is inevitable. Although the entire skeleton can help determine the sex, stature, and age of decayed, charred, or mutilated bodies at the scene of the crime, not constantly the whole skeleton is retrieved [5]. Sternum evaluation is one of the possible forensic examinations of skeletal remains. The Sternum is a flat bone in the middle of the anterior thoracic cage that shows a high recovery rate due to its endurability to a high degree of compression [2]. It is also one of the potential indicators of sex, age, and stature in forensic anthropological analysis. Studies using osteometry to determine the sex of an individual from the sternum have shown that the most helpful metric parameter for sexing a sternum is the total length of the sternum's body plus the manubrium sterni [10].

In homicides, mass disasters, road accidents, wildfires, plane mishaps, terrorist attacks, and conflicts, teeth, femur bone, humerus bone, sternum bone, clavicle bone, and other exhibits from unidentified dead bodies have been received in forensic laboratories. However, the sternum bone is a common exhibit. Because it contains a vast number of cells, the sternum bone is an excellent source for DNA profiling [10]. The sternum bone's costal cartilage, where the ribs join to the bone, produces a clear DNA profile. However, medical personnel should use caution while packing such bones for transport to forensic laboratories. They should prefer sternum bones in a plastic container with no preservatives or regular saline. The bones might be wrapped in cloth or wrapped in bits of paper. They should never use formaldehyde preservatives since they harm DNA [3]. DNA profiles derived from sternum bones can be used to build a DNA database at the state and national levels. Sternum bone is classified into two types based on the way of preservation. One is wet bone, along with some tissues, preserved in the non-porous container, and the other is wrapped in cloth and let dry in the ambient environment. A comparative Study of 30 sternums reported that the preparation and preservation of sternum samples affect the quality and quantity of DNA isolation and profiling. Plenty of DNA with better quality of complete DNA profiling can be obtained from a dry sternum than the quantity and quality of DNA obtained from a wet sternum preserved in a plastic container [5].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Samples

For this study, sternum samples (unidentified person) received in the forensic science laboratory were used for analysis. All samples, including 20 dry sternums, were examined most of them were missing identity cases. Manubrium of the sternum was taken for the extraction and isolation of DNA [4].

B. Experimental Workflow Design

C. Extraction of DNA

For extraction and isolation of DNA, the manubrium of sternum was selected. These bones had some tissue pieces over their surface. It was kept in a falcon tube filled with Milli-Q water on a rotator for 4-5 days to eliminate tissues from the bone surface. To avoid any contamination, water was changed regularly with fresh water in a 15ml tube. After washing the manubrium with water, carefully wrap the sternum in thick filter paper and dry it at room temperature. It could also be kept in an incubator at 40^o C for fast drying. The dried sample was then crushed into powdered form using a tissue crusher. Before isolation, it is essential to decalcify the bone; for this, 50 gm of powered bone was taken and put in 0.5M EDTA in a 2µl Eppendorf tube for 4-5 days. Supernatant EDTA contains calcium from bone powder [6]. To remove this calcium, EDTA was changed daily and further washed with normal saline and MilliQ water simultaneously. Add freshly prepared Prep Filer BTA lysis solution to the bone powder in a fresh lysate tube. After vortex and 5 mins centrifugation of the sample, incubate it at 56 °C in a thermal shaker for 4 hours. Centrifuged the lysate tube after incubation for 5 mins at 12,000 rpm and then transferred the clear lysate to a new sample tube followed by automated extraction [7].

AutoMate uses magnetic bead extraction methods as these beads bind to DNA for isolation. Instrumentation utilizes Prep Filer Express BTA™ chemistry packaged in a pre-filled, foil-sealed cartridge. This technique is adapted for better quality and quantity yield of DNA, especially for forensic samples. AutoMate doesn't need further processing by PCR and STR [8] analysis. Another advantage of this technique is it provides better DNA profiles without any experimental error, and can isolate 13 samples in 30 minutes. This technique can also improve the quality of DNA [19] [20]. The method is better than organic extraction as it is less time-consuming with the most negligible inhibition during the process.

D. Quantification of DNA

It is necessary to quantify the amount of DNA before PCR and DNA profiling, as only a narrow concentration of DNA can run in PCR. In the case of sternum samples, these were quantified using Quantifiler® Duo DNA Quantification kits of Applied Biosystems[9] [11]. Before quantification, reaction Mix and Primer Mix were added (12.5 µl and 10.5 µl per sample,

respectively) and mixed, followed by adding 2 μ l of sample to the well. The maximum volume of the polymerase chain reaction system is 25 μ l. To avoid contamination of the sample, it should be covered by the adhesive film on the plate. Quantification is conducted to know the amount of DNA present in each sample. The most popularly used technique in the laboratory for quantification is the Real-Time PCR or RT-PCR System [12]. Samples along with quantification standards were run as per standard instrumental protocols to determine the concentration of DNA present in the samples.

The Quantifiler® Duo kit contains dye-labeled Taq Man® probes for human-specific Ribonuclease RNA. The kit contains two more dyes, human male which is specific for sex-determining region, Y gene, and positive control. The final volume of eluted DNA is 25 μ l. The kits help to know that the sample contains human DNA. There are some advantages of using a duo kit as this may avoid misrepresentation of female sample, and male sample STR kits include the primer for amelogenin gene system and ascertained individualization and gender identification [16]. The study showed that the elimination of the Y allele in the amelogenin marker may be misrepresented as a female despite being male. RT-PCR is a better technique for confirmation of gender with the help of the Quantifiler® Duo kit [13].

III.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

DNA profiling has been proven to be one of the most potent and reliable techniques for establishing individuality from biological evidence. In this recent study, significant differences have been observed in the quantity and quality of the DNA extracted from dry & wet sternum owing to the distinct circumstances that the samples were exposed to [14] [15]. This suggests that DNA degradation arises with time and various environmental conditions that tend to degrade it. Time delay and environmental conditions have a negative impact on the forensic samples. In the case of degraded samples, different STR techniques worked best to get an accurate DNA profile. As per methodology, two different sets of samples of sternum were taken. Ten samples were kept without any preservatives in a plastic container, and ten samples were wrapped in a gauge and kept in an envelope. The samples, which dried naturally and were kept in an envelope, showed less degradation as compared to samples preserved in a plastic container. The comparative analysis of these bones has observed that the quantity of DNA isolated from the dry sternum was from 0.62 to 3.29 ng/ μ l, while the wet sternum showed quantity ranges from 1.06 ng/ μ l to 0.01 ng/ μ l. From the above results, it was found that the complete profile was generated from the dry sternum, which could not be done from the wet sternum.

Table 1: Quantitative chart of DNA in Dry Sternum bone samples.

S. No.	Dry Sternum Bone (DNA Qty.in ng/ μ l)	Wet Sternum Bone (DNA Qty. in ng/ μ l)
1.	1.00	0.04
2	2.32	0.06
3	1.09	0.25
4	0.62	0.20
5	2.42	0.15
6	1.62	0.01
7	1.99	0.32
8	2.04	1.06
9	0.70	0.98
10	3.29	0.32
11.	1.62.	1.09
12.	1.03	0.62
13.	0.82	2.42
14.	1.20	1.62
15.	2.08	1.99
16.	1.31	0.06
17.	0.69	0.25
18.	1.47	0.20
19.	1.96	1.12
20.	1.12	0.07

Fig. 1 Comparative histogram of DNA quantity from the dry and wet sternum.

It is very clear from the results of this study that the quantity of wet sternum was comparatively less than that of dry sternum. It can be caused by environmental and allied factors that affect the quantity of DNA. It was also observed that bone samples have given a better result of good quality and quantity of DNA, which were dried in natural condition compared to bone preserved in a plastic container. A study was conducted by Naresh Kumar and his colleagues on the preservation of the sternum of unidentified bodies, which affects DNA profiling, and advised that formalin also results in degraded DNA and leads to abridged DNA quality [17] [18]. The result indicates the quantity of DNA isolated from the dry sternum was 0.62 to 3.29 ng/ μ l, while the wet sternum showed the quantity of DNA isolated from 1.06- 0.01 ng/ μ l. The accurate profile was generated from the dry sternum, which could not be done from the wet sternum.

IV. CONCLUSION

DNA profiling is considered one of the most accurate and reliable techniques for disaster victim identification. This technique requires post-mortem DNA samples as well as ante-mortem DNA samples of the suspected victim. If no ante-mortem sample is available, then a sample from a biological relative can be collected. Collection of post-mortem DNA samples is complicated as the risk of DNA contamination is high due to unfavourable conditions at mass disasters and different preservation techniques for human remains. It helps us to establish an identity even from completely degraded dead bodies/ skeleton remnants. In these cases, we still have chances to extract DNA from hard tissues like bones and teeth as skeletal are made up of calcareous material, which is difficult to degrade. Some specific contaminants in samples and misinterpreting facts may result in false results. Although advancements in the field of DNA profiling have helped police and the justice system to identify the culprit, profiling is more reliable and accurate when kept side by side with other evidence.

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